

27 **Keywords**

28 Cartilage replacement, hydrogels, biotribology, biochemistry

29

30 **1. Introduction**

31 Hydrogels have emerged as a promising class of biomaterials for cartilage replacement due to
32 their high-water content, biocompatibility, and mechanical properties [1]. The ability of hydrogels to
33 mimic the extracellular matrix of native cartilage makes them suitable candidates for tunable tissue
34 engineering applications [2]. Additionally, their viscoelastic properties allow them to absorb
35 mechanical loads while maintaining a hydrated environment, which is essential for proper cartilage
36 function. However, challenges remain in optimizing their biochemical behavior, mechanical strength,
37 durability, and lubrication properties to withstand the high loads and shear stresses experienced in
38 articulating joints [3]. Moreover, the degradation behavior and long-term stability of hydrogel-based
39 implants require further study to ensure their viability as long-term solutions in clinical applications
40 [4].

41 Current studies on hydrogel-based cartilage replacements focus on enhancing their
42 mechanical properties through crosslinking strategies, composite formulations, and reinforcement
43 with nano- or microparticles to improve load-bearing capacity. Synthetic hydrogels such as poly(vinyl
44 alcohol) (PVA) and poly(2-hydroxyethyl methacrylate) (pHEMA) have been investigated for their
45 structural integrity and ability to retain moisture, which is critical for lubrication in joint applications
46 [1],[4]. Additionally, biotribological evaluations have demonstrated that the lubrication and wear
47 resistance of hydrogels depend on their surface roughness, polymer network architecture, and the
48 presence of synovial fluid components [5]. Studies have also explored the impact of different
49 fabrication techniques on hydrogel performance [1]. One key challenge for hydrogel formulations is
50 achieving sufficient mechanical strength while maintaining flexibility. Studies have shown that
51 reinforcing hydrogels with bacterial cellulose-polyvinyl alcohol (BC-PVA) networks significantly
52 enhances their mechanical properties, making them more comparable to native cartilage [6].

53 Furthermore, double-network hydrogels incorporating polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) and poly(2-acrylamido-
54 2-methyl-1-propanesulfonic acid sodium salt) (PAMPS) have been engineered to achieve cartilage-
55 equivalent mechanical robustness [2]. Additionally, investigations indicate that integrating bioactive
56 molecules, such as growth factors or lubricating proteins, can enhance cellular interactions and further
57 optimize hydrogel performance for tissue engineering applications [3]. However, balancing these
58 mechanical enhancements with the material's viscoelasticity remains a crucial aspect of ongoing
59 research. Compared to this, the second pHEMA hydrogel is a biocompatible and cytocompatible
60 polymer with minimal immune response, making it suitable for various biomedical uses. It has been
61 applied in bone regeneration [7], wound healing [8], cancer therapy [9], and ophthalmic devices [10]-
62 [12]. Moreover, pHEMA-based hydrogels demonstrate outstanding flexibility, transparency,
63 mechanical strength, and biocompatibility. A major advantage lies in their tunable mechanical and
64 optical properties, which can be readily adjusted by modifying key factors such as the crosslinking
65 method or monomer concentration. Thanks to its favorable mechanical and biological characteristics,
66 pHEMA is also considered a promising material for cartilage replacements [13],[14].

67 The biotribological performance of hydrogels is influenced by multiple factors, including
68 surface roughness, asperity size, and the interaction between polymer networks and synovial fluid
69 constituents [15]. Studies have shown that hydrogels with microtextured surfaces can significantly
70 reduce friction under physiological conditions, mimicking the low-friction properties of native cartilage
71 [16]. Furthermore, hydration lubrication mechanisms play a crucial role in minimizing wear and
72 ensuring long-term functionality, with recent advances highlighting the synergistic effects of surface-
73 bound lubricating molecules and hydrogel elasticity [3]. Another crucial aspect of hydrogel lubrication
74 is the role of interfacial water layers, which can form a protective barrier against mechanical wear.
75 Recent findings suggest that hydrogels with high hydrophilicity and optimized crosslinking densities
76 exhibit improved boundary lubrication, reducing friction coefficients to levels comparable with native
77 cartilage [17]. Additionally, studies have investigated polymer brush coatings, such as zwitterionic
78 PMPC layers, which exhibit extremely low friction coefficients due to their hydration lubrication effect

79 [3]. Furthermore, adaptive lubrication mechanisms in hydrogels, influenced by the interaction of
80 polymer structures with synovial fluid components, have been reported to enhance wear resistance
81 [4].

82 Despite significant advancements, there remains a need to develop hydrogel formulations that
83 offer a balance between mechanical robustness and superior lubrication properties. The ability to fine-
84 tune hydrogel properties through polymer composition, crosslinking strategies, and surface
85 modifications remains a critical area of exploration [18]. Additionally, assessing the mechanical
86 behavior and structural stability of hydrogel-based cartilage replacements under load-bearing
87 conditions is crucial for their effective application [4]. This study aims to evaluate the biochemical,
88 mechanical and biotribological performance of novel hydrogel composites intended for cartilage
89 replacement. By systematically analyzing the effects of polymer composition and biotribological
90 interactions, we seek to advance the design of hydrogel-based materials that closely replicate the
91 functional properties of natural cartilage. This study aims to bridge the gap between fundamental
92 hydrogel science and the engineering of next-generation cartilage-mimicking materials by elucidating
93 the interplay between structure, chemistry, and tribological performance.

94

95 **2. Materials and methods**

96 **Synthesis of pHEMA hydrogel samples**

97 For the synthesis of both types of pHEMA hydrogels, 2-hydroxyethyl methacrylate (HEMA, monomer),
98 2,2-dimethoxy-2-phenylacetophenone (DMPA, photo-initiator), and ethylene glycol dimethacrylate
99 (EGDMA, crosslinker) were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich (Germany) and Acros Organics (Thermo Fisher
100 Scientific, UK). MilliQ Type 1 water (ISO 3696) was produced using a Millipore purification system
101 (MilliQ Academic, France). Hyaluronic acid (HA) with a molecular weight of 820–1,020 kg.mol⁻¹ for the
102 preparation of simplified model synovial fluid (SMSF) was purchased from Contipro a.s. (Czech
103 Republic. A high-intensity UV lamp with a wavelength of 365 nm and 18 W output, was obtained from
104 Eurolite (Germany).

105 pHEMA hydrogels were synthesised with minor modification according to [10] via UV-initiated free-
106 radical polymerisation of HEMA (60% w/w), EGDMA (1% w/w), and DMPA (0.5% w/w) in MilliQ water,
107 under nitrogen (labeled pHEMA N₂) or ambient atmosphere (23 °C, 28% RH). The mixture was cast into
108 fixed-volume moulds on tribological glass and irradiated with a 365 nm, 18 W UV lamp (10 cm
109 distance) for 20 min. More detailed information regarding pHEMA synthesis may be found in our
110 previous study [13].

111

112 **Preparation of PVA hydrogel samples**

113 PVA hydrogel samples were prepared using a standardized multi-step protocol based on thermal
114 dissolution of PVA and subsequent physical crosslinking. The PVA solution was formulated by dissolving
115 15 wt% of poly(vinyl alcohol) powder (Kuraray Co., Ltd.; degree of polymerization: 1700;
116 saponification: 98–99 mol%) in distilled water. Two identical batches were stirred at 500 rpm while the
117 PVA powder was added slowly to avoid agglomeration. After initial homogenization, the closed vessels
118 containing the solution were heated in a water bath setup to maintain the solution temperature
119 between 90 °C and 95 °C. Stirring was continued for 2–3 hours with gradually decreasing revolutions
120 (from 300 rpm to ~60–80 rpm) to accommodate increasing viscosity. The resulting transparent
121 solution was cooled to room temperature for 2 hours under continued mild stirring (120 rpm). After
122 surface film removal, 30 g of the PVA solution was cast into polystyrene dishes (9 cm diameter) for
123 hydrogel fabrication. Air bubbles were removed manually using a pipette.

124 The CP06 hydrogel samples were prepared via a combined cast-drying and freeze–thaw method (CP
125 process). Following solution casting, dishes were sealed and subjected to a single freeze–thaw cycle (–
126 20 °C for 8 h → 4 °C for 16 h), followed by high-temperature drying under controlled conditions (60 °C,
127 80% RH, 6 hours). The partially dried samples were then subjected to a second freeze–thaw cycle of
128 the same parameters and finally exposed to low-temperature drying (8 °C, 50% RH) until water content
129 fell below 12%, typically after 4–5 days. Dried gels were immersed in distilled water (1 L per sample)

130 and left to swell for 3 days. The bottom surface (i.e., the one in contact with the dish) was marked and
131 used as the sliding surface for subsequent tribological testing.

132 The LM hydrogels were fabricated as a bilayer system, consisting of a freeze–thaw (FT) base layer and
133 a cast-dried (CD) top layer. First, a dose of PVA solution was subjected to four FT cycles (–20 °C for 8 h,
134 4 °C for 16 h each). A second layer (CD) was then cast onto the FT base and dried at 20 °C and 50% RH.
135 The drying was continued until residual water content was below 12%, which typically required ~3
136 days. After swelling in distilled water for 3 days, the upper surface of the laminar construct (the one
137 exposed to air during drying) was used as the sliding surface. All samples were stored in distilled water
138 at 4 °C prior to characterization. Further details about the hydrogel preparation may be found in [19].

139

140 **2.1 Characterization of materials**

141 **Static swelling test**

142 PVA hydrogel samples in the form of 10 mm compact discs were left to dry in a laboratory oven (EcoCell
143 111, Thermo Fisher Scientific, Czech Republic) at a temperature of 50 °C until they reached a constant
144 weight. The average thickness of dried PVA CP06 (transparent) and layered PVA (opaque) was 1.38 ± 0.4
145 and 1.82 ± 0.4 mm, respectively. A SMSF solution, consisting of 0.5% w/v hyaluronic acid (HA) in Milli-Q
146 water, was prepared and used for the swelling experiments. The hydrogel samples were immersed in
147 the model synovial fluid and incubated at 37 °C. After the selected time points (0.5, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 24,
148 26, 29, 48, and 72 hours) of incubation, the samples were gently wiped with a lint-free cloth to remove
149 surface moisture, and water uptake was quantified gravimetrically. Each experiment was conducted in
150 quintuplicate ($n = 5$), and the swelling ratio of the hydrogels was calculated according to Equation 1.

$$151 \quad \text{Swelling ratio (\%)} = \frac{W_1 - W_0}{W_0} \cdot 100 \quad (\text{Eq. 1})$$

152

153 where W_0 is the initial weight of the dried sample and W_1 is the weight of the swollen sample at the
154 defined time interval.

155 A first-order swelling kinetic model was used to fit the experimental data and to calculate the swelling
156 parameters according to Equation 2 [20],[21].

$$157 \quad \frac{dS}{dt} = k_1 \cdot (S_{max} - S) \quad (Eq. 2)$$

158 where k_1 is the rate constant for first-order swelling kinetics, S is the degree of swelling at a specific
159 time point, and S_{max} is the degree of swelling at equilibrium.

161 The first-order (k_1) swelling constant and S_{max} were calculated by fitting the experimental data to the
162 model in Excel using the function 'Solver' with the parameters set to be larger than or equal to zero.

163

164 **Dynamic mechanical analysis**

165 Compression tests were performed on the swollen hydrogels (for 72 h) using dynamic mechanical
166 analysis (DMA) on the DHR-2 instrument (TA Instruments), equipped with cross-hatched plate-to-plate
167 geometry (diameter 20 mm). Tests were conducted in time sweep mode at constant conditions:
168 temperature of 25 °C, frequency of 1 Hz, and displacement amplitude of 12 μm. This corresponded to
169 ≤ 1 % compressive strain, ensuring the measurements remained within the linear-viscoelastic region
170 while applying the same absolute deformation to every specimen regardless of height. For the
171 compression tests, the samples were shaped into circles with a precise cutting tool (standardized
172 punch, diameter 20 mm). Prior to measurement, each sample was compressed to a normal force of
173 2.5 N and allowed to relax for 2 min.

174

175 **Surface morphology**

176 The surface features of dried PVA hydrogel samples were examined using scanning electron
177 microscopy (SEM). Prior to SEM analysis, the samples, dried to constant weight in a laboratory oven
178 (Ecocell 111) at 50 °C, were coated with a 15 nm-thick gold layer using a Leica EM ACE600 coater (Leica,
179 Germany). Imaging was performed using a MIRA3-XMU microscope (Tescan, Czech Republic) at

180 appropriate magnifications and a working distance, with an accelerating voltage of 5 kV. Images were
181 processed using ImageJ 2 software (National Institutes of Health, USA).

182

183 **2.2 Pin-on-plate friction and wear tests**

184 A commercial tribometer (Bruker UMT TriboLab) was employed to perform reciprocating sliding
185 experiments. This device allows for multiple test configurations suitable for studying tribological
186 behaviour. In this study, two setups were used: a pin-on-plate configuration with CoCrMo-on-PVA and
187 cartilage-on-PVA contact pairs. Details of the experimental settings and lubricant composition are
188 provided in *Tab. 1* and *Tab. 2*.

189 Friction measurements were obtained using a load cell module integrated into the slider mechanism.
190 The module included a biaxial load cell and sensors that maintained a constant normal force of 5 N and
191 recorded the corresponding tangential force. The load cell had a maximum capacity of 50 N. The slider
192 produced a consistent linear motion driven by a stepper motor (see *Fig. 1*). Data collected at the stroke
193 reversals, where the sliding speed dropped below the target value, were excluded from the analysis.
194 As outlined in *Tab. 1*, two sets of tests were performed: friction tests and wear tests. These differed in
195 both the type of sliding pin used and the test duration. To ensure statistical robustness, each test was
196 repeated five times with cartilage and three times with the CoCrMo pin. Based on initial trials, where
197 negligible wear was observed on both cartilage and polished CoCrMo surfaces, the CoCrMo pin was
198 intentionally roughened to a surface roughness of $S_a = 530$ nm for the main wear experiment.

199

200 **Table 1:** Experimental conditions of friction and wear tests.

	Friction test	Wear test
Material	PVA (CP06, LM) pHEMA (air, nitrogen)	
Load	5 N	
Stroke	12 mm	
Lubricant	synovial fluid	
Speed	10 mm.s ⁻¹	
Pin (ϕ)	9.7 mm	
Pin material	cartilage	CoCrMo

No of cycles	750	7500
Duration	30 min	5 hours
Repetition	5 times	3 times

201

202 **Table 2:** The composition of a simplified model synovial fluid (SMSF). Albumin (Sigma-Aldrich A7030);
 203 γ -globulin (Sigma-Aldrich G5009); phospholipids (Sigma-Aldrich P3782).

	Albumin	γ-globulin	Hyaluronic acid	Phospholipids
Concentration (mg/ml)	20	3.6	2.5	0.15

204

205

Figure 1: Tribometer experimental setup.

206

207

208 2.3 Surface topography analysis

209 Additionally, both untested and worn samples were examined using optical scanning microscopy
 210 (OSM, Keyence VHX 7000). The scanned surfaces were assessed visually and by measuring volume loss.

211 Optical evaluation focused only on samples that had been subjected to sliding with the roughened
 212 CoCrMo pin. The observation procedure is illustrated in *Fig. 2*. For each sliding track, three images (2
 213 \times 10 mm) were captured at a predefined location, marked with a crosshair using an alcohol-based pen.

214 Images were taken both before and after the test to enable volume loss assessment, as shown on the
 215 right side of *Fig. 2*.

216

217

218

Figure 2: Left: virgin sample; middle: worn sample;

219

right: illustration of the data obtained from scanned areas.

220

221 3. Results

222 3.1 Swelling Capacity, DMA and surface morphology

223 The swelling behavior of two types of PVA hydrogels, specifically a transparent monolayered PVA CP06
 224 and an opaque, layered PVA, was investigated in a SMSF containing 0.5% w/v hyaluronic acid (HA) in
 225 Milli-Q water. The data were subsequently fitted to first-order kinetic equations, and the first-order
 226 swelling constant (k_1) along with the degree of swelling at equilibrium (S_{max}) were calculated (Tab. 3)
 227 using the Excel 'Solver' function.

228

229 **Table 3:** Calculated first-order swelling rate constant k_1 , correlation coefficient R2, and the predicted
 230 degree of swelling at equilibrium S_{max} of the PVA CP06 and layered PVA LM. The data for the pHEMA
 231 hydrogels synthesized under varying atmospheres in a SMSF were retracted from our previous
 232 publication [13].

	PVA CP06	PVA LM	pHEMA N ₂ [13]	pHEMA air [13]
k_1 (h ⁻¹)	0.26±0.01	0.16±0.01	1.29±0.54	1.04±0.29
R2 (-)	0.99±0.00	0.99±0.01	0.98±0.01	0.97±0.02
S_{max} (%)	235.57±2.94	219.91±4.91	53.61±2.40	60.32±9.45

233

234 The PVA and pHEMA hydrogels exhibit distinct swelling behaviors in environments containing
 235 hyaluronic acid, which are influenced by their material properties and mechanisms of interaction with

236 the SMSF components. As illustrated in Fig. 3, PVA hydrogels (represented by the blue and purple
237 curves) demonstrate a high swelling capacity in hyaluronic acid-containing environments.
238

239
240 **Figure 3:** Swelling ratios of the two distinct PVA hydrogels compared to the pHEMA hydrogels
241 prepared under nitrogen and laboratory atmospheres in a SMSF. The time points were fitted using a
242 first-order swelling kinetic model. The data for the pHEMA N₂ and pHEMA air were retracted from
243 our recent publication [13].
244

245 PVA hydrogels prepared via the freeze-thaw method develop a macroporous network that enhances
246 the absorption of aqueous solvents [22]. In our study, both hydrogel types exhibited rapid swelling
247 [23], reaching equilibrium after 24 hours of submersion in SMSF, after which their water content
248 remained stable. The equilibrium swelling ratios for PVA LM and CP06 were $218.1 \pm 4.1\%$ and
249 $234.5 \pm 7.0\%$, respectively. The slightly higher swelling ratio of the single-layered CP06 hydrogel can be
250 attributed to its structure, consisting of a single PVA layer subjected to two freeze-drying cycles. In
251 contrast, the PVA LM hydrogel is composed of a layered structure combining four freeze-drying cycles
252 with cast-drying, which contributes to its comparatively lower swelling. Freeze-drying promotes the
253 formation of a macroporous structure in the hydrogel, further enhancing water uptake and swelling
254 rate [24]. On the other hand, cast-drying results in a denser network due to tighter hydrogen bonding
255 and reduced porosity, which limits the swelling capacity [25],[26]. Additionally, the formation of extra
256 hydrogen bonds during cast-drying further restricts the rehydration potential of the hydrogel in

257 simulated body fluids. It is also notable that an increased number of freeze-drying cycles leads to
258 reduced swelling in freeze-dried PVA hydrogels [27]. Thus, both the number of freeze-drying cycles
259 and the inclusion of cast-dried PVA layers influenced the swelling behavior observed in the PVA LM
260 hydrogels.

261 In comparison, the pHEMA hydrogel exhibited a significantly lower swelling ratio, primarily due to its
262 denser and more rigid polymer network formed by chemical crosslinking. This structure contains fewer
263 accessible hydrophilic groups, which delays and limits the overall water absorption [28],[29]. Although
264 the chemical structure of pHEMA retains some hydrophilicity, it does not match the swelling potential
265 of PVA, resulting in restricted swelling in water and biological fluids. In contrast, PVA hydrogels,
266 composed of long polymer chains uniformly distributed with hydroxyl groups, form a flexible and
267 highly hydrophilic network. This allows extensive hydrogen bonding with water molecules, enabling
268 greater swelling capacity [30],[31]. As we reported in our previous study [13], bovine articular cartilage
269 swells rapidly in SMSF, reaching a swelling ratio of $222.8 \pm 43.3\%$ within several hours. Therefore, in
270 terms of swelling behavior, the layered PVA LM hydrogel presents a promising candidate for mimicking
271 the response of bovine articular cartilage in simulated synovial fluid.

272

273 **Dynamic Mechanical Analysis**

274 DMA was used to obtain a more detailed understanding of the mechanical behavior of the material
275 under dynamic loading, which is closely related to its tribological properties. Time-sweep compression
276 tests (25 °C, 1 Hz, 12 μm) showed that all hydrogels were elastic-dominated ($E' \gg E''$). The two PVA
277 hydrogels, CP-06 and LM, exhibited the highest initial stiffness (≈ 110 kPa and ≈ 90 kPa, respectively)
278 and remained essentially unchanged, indicating excellent mechanical stability. In contrast, the pHEMA
279 hydrogels (N_2 and air) displayed a gradual increase in both moduli, a behaviour typical of dehydration-
280 driven densification reported for pHEMA networks [32]. *Fig. 4* displays a complex modulus E^*
281 calculated following equation 3.

$$282 \quad E^* = \sqrt{E'^2 + E''^2} \quad (Eq. 3)$$

283 where E' refers to storage modulus (MPa) and E'' is the loss modulus (MPa).

284

285

286 **Figure 4:** Development of the complex modulus during time-sweep tests for four hydrogel systems at
287 25 °C, 1 Hz, $\leq 1\%$ strain. *The semi-transparent data points (pHEMA hydrogels) correspond to results
288 that were previously published as supplementary material in our earlier study [13].

289 *Fig. 5* shows an example of the morphology of all hydrogel samples observed under SEM. On close
290 examination, it can be noticed that the surface of the pHEMA-air sample has an unmistakable wrinkled
291 surface (*Fig. 5C*), while PVA CP06 (*Fig. 5A*) shows fine wrinkling. On the other hand, the PVA LM sample
292 (*Fig. 5B*) already shows a smooth surface compared to PVA CP06. A similar smooth surface morphology
293 of the pure PVA sample was demonstrated by Jayaramudu et al. [33]. The pHEMA N₂ sample exhibits
294 a smooth and homogeneous morphology, as evidenced by its uniform surface texture (*Fig. 5D*).

295

296

Figure 5: SEM images of dried hydrogel samples:

297

A) PVA CP06, B) PVA LM, C) pHEMA air, and D) pHEMA N₂.

298

3.2 Friction analysis

300 The sliding experiments against the cartilage pin revealed a pronounced difference in the coefficient
 301 of friction (COF) between PVA and pHEMA samples (*Fig. 6, top*). After 750 cycles, the pHEMA-N₂ sample
 302 exhibited a COF of 0.086, while pHEMA-air reached 0.026. In contrast, PVA LM and CP06 demonstrated
 303 markedly lower friction values of 0.008 and 0.006, respectively. This ultra-low friction performance is
 304 counterbalanced by the difficulty of preserving surface smoothness during PVA fabrication, which
 305 remains a critical limitation in material selection. Even minor surface irregularities lead to an increase
 306 in COF – though the rise remains negligible compared to pHEMA.

307 When the sliding pin was replaced with CoCrMo, the disparity between the hydrogel types became
 308 even more evident (*Fig. 6, bottom*). PVA samples maintained low friction levels in the range of 0.010–
 309 0.016, whereas pHEMA showed a significant increase in COF – approximately an order of magnitude
 310 higher than in the cartilage pin setup. From a purely frictional standpoint, the hydrogels performed in
 311 the following order (from best to worst): PVA CP06 ≈ PVA LM << pHEMA-N₂ < pHEMA-air.

312

313 **Figure 6:** Friction comparison of PVA and pHEMA hydrogels sliding against cartilage pin (top), and
314 roughened CoCrMo pin (bottom).

315

316 **3.3 Wear analysis**

317 The topography and volume loss of the hydrogel samples were assessed using optical scanning
318 microscopy (OSM). The pHEMA-air samples displayed a visibly wavy surface, whereas pHEMA-N₂
319 formed a smoother and more uniform layer. In contrast, PVA samples, crosslinked exclusively in air,
320 consistently resulted in smooth surfaces, with PVA CP06 exhibiting Ra = 1.53 μm and PVA LM Ra = 1.37
321 μm.

322 In relation to the COF results, reduced wear was anticipated for PVA samples, which maintained
323 friction values around 0.01, compared to 0.2 and 0.7 for pHEMA. The scanned surfaces revealed some
324 volumetric differences between pHEMA and PVA samples, suggesting slightly lower volume loss in
325 pHEMA hydrogels (*Fig. 7*). However, it must be acknowledged that the reliability of these
326 measurements is limited. Hydrogel surfaces experienced considerable drying during scanning, which
327 proved challenging to control. The convex geometry of the PVA samples was only partially corrected
328 in the sliding direction; in the transverse direction, surface curvature persisted. As a result, the scanned
329 depth varied across the surface, leading to scanning times of 10 to 30 minutes per image. These issues
330 were less prominent in pHEMA samples, which contained lower water content and exhibited a more
331 uniform thickness. Additional correlation plots between friction, wear, swelling capacity and
332 mechanical stiffness are provided in the Supplementary Information file (*Section S1, Fig. S1*).

333

334 **Figure 7:** Representative images of scanned hydrogel samples and their estimated volume loss after
 335 wear test.

336

337

4. Discussion

338

339 The lowest friction coefficients of 0.006 and 0.008 were measured for PVA CP06 and PVA LM,
 340 respectively, when articulating against a cartilage pin. Both showed excellent statistical repeatability.

341

342 Friction of such low magnitude is typically associated with superlubrication – a state of nearly
 343 frictionless motion. pHEMA-based hydrogels exhibited approximately 3- to 8-fold higher coefficients

344

345 of friction. A promising result was observed for pHEMA (air), which showed a stable COF of 0.026
 346 throughout the experiment, comparable to PVA. In contrast, pHEMA polymerized in a nitrogen

347

348 atmosphere showed lower repeatability and a gradually increasing COF. These results may be
 349 explained by the different water content and permeability of the hydrogel samples. As shown in Fig.

350

351 8, the PVA samples stood out with the highest water content ($\approx 73\%$) compared to pHEMA hydrogels
 352 (N_2 : 54%, air: 61%). It is worth noting that our previous study [13] reported a coefficient of friction of

353

354 approximately 0.016 for cartilage-on-cartilage articulation under similar test conditions. This
 355 physiological value serves as a useful benchmark for interpreting the present results. While both PVA

356

350 hydrogels exhibited even lower COF values in this setup, such performance must be balanced against
 351 other factors such as wear resistance and long-term durability.

352

353

354 **Figure 8:** Comparison of properties influencing the tribological properties of hydrogels at the
 355 reciprocal test. Note: Raw data comes from virgin samples; the permeability of CP06 and LM is
 356 estimated based on [34],[35]. The expected load partitioning is estimated according to [36].

357

358 The excellent performance of both PVA samples can be attributed to a high degree of fluid load support
 359 and only minimal solid-to-solid contact. Consistent with the water content, the COF trend of the
 360 pHEMA samples follows the order CP06 < LM < (air) << (N₂), see Fig. 6. An important factor contributing
 361 to good lubrication is the permeability of interstitial water. However, despite its importance, the
 362 permeability of cartilage is relatively low (approximately 10^{-15} to 10^{-16} m²), which allows for optimal
 363 fluid outflow and uptake under load. Higher permeability, as seen in pHEMA (N₂) or PVA FT [34]
 364 typically results in higher friction. The exceptional lubrication of PVA is likely further supported by
 365 highly hydrated surfaces formed by protruding surface polymer chains [15]. Additionally, the bumpy
 366 surface of pHEMA (air) may contribute to the low COF by acting as a lubricant reservoir (enhancing
 367 elastohydrodynamic lubrication) and by facilitating additional biphasic squeeze-out, see Fig. 9. This
 368 unique surface morphology of the pHEMA-air hydrogel may stem from oxygen inhibition during photo-
 369 polymerization, which is known to interfere with free-radical chain propagation near the polymer-air
 370 interface [37]. As a result, the uppermost layer of the hydrogel exhibits reduced crosslinking density

371 and a more irregular polymer network. This leads to a locally softer and more hydrated region with
 372 elevated permeability and enhanced fluid mobility. The presence of this surface-modified layer not
 373 only lowers the coefficient of friction due to improved hydration lubrication but also facilitates rapid
 374 fluid exchange near the interface [38]. Despite the low permeability of the bulk material, this localized
 375 permeability allows for temporary fluid pressurization during loading while enabling the regeneration
 376 of the lubrication layer between cycles, thereby sustaining low friction throughout repeated
 377 articulation.

378

Figure 9: Explanation of long-term wear test results with CoCrMo pin.

379

380

381 Beyond physical surface features, the observed differences in friction performance between PVA and
 382 pHEMA hydrogels may also be attributed to their inherent chemical structure and resulting affinity for
 383 water. PVA contains numerous hydroxyl (–OH) groups along its polymer backbone, readily forming
 384 hydrogen bonds with surrounding water molecules. This promotes the formation of a stable hydration
 385 layer at the hydrogel surface, facilitating low-friction sliding under aqueous conditions. In contrast,
 386 pHEMA possesses only a single –OH group per monomer and a predominantly hydrophobic
 387 methacrylate backbone, resulting in a lower density of hydrogen bonding interactions. Consequently,
 388 pHEMA hydrogels exhibit weaker surface hydration and less effective boundary lubrication, which may
 389 contribute to their consistently higher coefficients of friction. These findings are consistent with the
 390 swelling data, where PVA samples demonstrated significantly greater water uptake, reflecting their
 391 stronger hydrophilic character.

392 The interplay between mechanical stiffness and frictional performance appears to differ substantially
393 between PVA and pHEMA hydrogels. In PVA, increased compressive modulus has been correlated with
394 reduced friction coefficients [39], suggesting that enhanced structural integrity contributes to better
395 load support and fluid retention during articulation. In contrast, pHEMA hydrogels tend to achieve
396 lower friction when the surface is soft and swollen, implying that surface hydration and chemistry
397 dominate lubrication behavior rather than stiffness alone [38]. These observations highlight that
398 distinct lubrication mechanisms are at play depending on the polymer's structure and interaction with
399 the surrounding medium.

400 During testing with the cartilage pin, no visible wear was observed on the hydrogel samples. Therefore,
401 a roughened CoCrMo pin ($S_a = 530$ nm) was used as a counter surface. The results showed the same
402 sample ranking based on their COF. The PVA samples maintained approximately the same friction level
403 as in the cartilage test (≈ 0.015), slightly increasing as wear progressed. A major difference was
404 observed for the pHEMA samples, where the COF increased by up to 10 times (e.g. air: $0.026 \rightarrow 0.206$)
405 compared to the cartilage test, see *Fig. 6*. The COF trend of the pHEMA samples remained either stable
406 or slightly decreasing over time. Interestingly, the lowest wear was not observed in the PVA samples –
407 despite their lowest COF – but in the pHEMA samples, see *Fig. 7*. This phenomenon is likely due to the
408 higher elastic modulus, which correlates with greater material strength and thus reduced susceptibility
409 to damage from hard asperities during solid-to-solid contact (e.g. CP06 = 0.51 MPa, pHEMA (air) = 0.93
410 MPa). Surprisingly, the lowest wear was found in pHEMA (N_2) (0.0197 mm²), even though its modulus
411 was lower than that of pHEMA (air). This result may be explained by the bumpy surface of the air-
412 polymerized hydrogel, which likely caused higher initial (run-in) wear. However, it is expected that
413 once the protrusions are worn away, the wear rate of the (air) hydrogel will decrease. It should also be
414 noted that the wear measurement technique had limitations. Significant drying of the PVA samples
415 under ambient conditions made it difficult to compare the actual shape differences between the
416 unworn and worn samples. This issue was not observed in the pHEMA hydrogels due to their lower

417 water content. Therefore, direct wear comparison between PVA and pHEMA should be interpreted
418 cautiously.

419 From the perspective of biochemical material characterization, in both PVA LM and PVA CP06
420 hydrogels, the swelling behavior adheres to first-order kinetics, with average k_1 values of 0.16 ± 0.01
421 and $0.26 \pm 0.1 \text{ h}^{-1}$, respectively. Both hydrogels demonstrated substantial media absorption capacity
422 within the initial 24 hours [24], achieving $218.1 \pm 4.1\%$ for the PVA LM and $234.5 \pm 7.0\%$ for the PVA CP06,
423 which is comparable to the results reported for freeze-thawed PVA hydrogels in PBS by Asy-Syifa et al.
424 [39]. The pronounced swelling capacity of the PVA hydrogels is attributed to their hydrophilic nature
425 and the porous three-dimensional (3D) structure formed through the freeze-thaw cycles during
426 hydrogel preparation [41]. Subsequently, the swelling ratio did not increase, indicating an equilibrium
427 state.

428 Upon immersion in the aqueous medium, the dried polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) chains are densely
429 arranged. The SMSF infiltrates the polymer and initiates the formation of hydrogen bonds with the
430 hydroxyl groups of PVA in the region with a low swelling ratio. As reported by Krzeminski, et al. [42],
431 the aqueous medium forms hydrogen bonds either with the hydroxyl groups located on the surfaces
432 of polymer crystallites or with other available hydroxyl groups [43]. Water that does not form hydrogen
433 bonds with the PVA hydroxyl groups results in the formation of condensation water species, which are
434 responsible for the increased values of equilibrium swelling and the formation of additional intra- and
435 intermolecular hydrogen bonds. Furthermore, PVA hydrogels generally demonstrate enhanced water
436 absorption in the presence of hyaluronic acid and improved lubrication properties, thereby mimicking
437 the behavior of a natural joint [22]. The LM and CP06 hydrogels vary in the methodology in preparation
438 – the PVA CP06 hydrogels contain a single layer formed by two FT cycles. In contrast, the PVA LM
439 hydrogels are formed by two layers, with the bottom layer formed by four FT cycles and the upper
440 layer formed by CD. The maximum swelling ratio of the CP06 and LM hydrogels achieved after 72 hours
441 was $232.1 \pm 6.8\%$ and $215.6 \pm 5.8\%$, respectively. This difference can be attributed to differences in the
442 network structure and fabrication methods. It is well-established that the number of freeze-thaw

443 cycles enhances crystallinity and crosslink density in the PVA hydrogels, forming a denser network that
444 restricts water absorption [44]. In the PVA LM, the base layer underwent four freeze-thaw cycles,
445 resulting in reduced swelling compared to the PVA CP06. Additionally, the presence of an interfacial
446 region between layers [45] can hinder media diffusion and impose mechanical constraints, further
447 limiting swelling [24],[46]. Previous studies have shown that prolonged freeze-thaw cycling modifies
448 pore architecture [47], often resulting in fewer but larger pores and increased 'freezable' water
449 content, which collectively reduces overall swelling potential [48]. Furthermore, hydrogels with higher
450 crosslink density exhibit increased mechanical stiffness, resisting volumetric expansion under
451 physiological-like osmotic conditions such as those in an SMSF [49].

452 The low wear characteristics and structural stability observed in pHEMA hydrogels suggest that,
453 despite their higher friction, these materials may serve as a robust platform for further material
454 optimization. Future research may focus on enhancing their lubrication performance through the
455 incorporation of biofunctional components such as hyaluronic acid or phospholipids, aiming to mimic
456 the biochemical complexity of natural synovial environments. Such modifications could improve
457 boundary lubrication and interfacial hydration without compromising the mechanical integrity of the
458 base hydrogel. Given its resistance to long-term degradation under load, pHEMA may thus be
459 particularly well suited for advanced tailoring toward cartilage replacement, where both mechanical
460 resilience and adaptive lubrication are required.

461 Last but not least, some limitations of the study and future perspectives should be addressed. First,
462 although volumetric wear was assessed using optical scanning microscopy, the methodology was
463 partially limited by surface drying and geometrical deviations, particularly in the convex PVA samples.
464 These artefacts may have influenced the absolute volume loss values and warrant careful
465 interpretation. Future studies could benefit from the use of hydrated-state or in situ imaging
466 techniques to obtain more robust wear measurements. Second, while fluid permeability is a known
467 factor influencing interfacial lubrication and load support in hydrated biomaterials, no direct
468 permeability measurements were performed in this study. Instead, permeability-related behavior was

469 inferred from swelling data and literature-reported trends. Dedicated permeability characterization of
470 the developed hydrogel systems, including pressure-driven or osmotic flow analysis, remains an
471 important direction for future work to fully elucidate their lubrication mechanisms. Third, this study
472 focused on a simplified model of synovial fluid. The use of more physiologically complete lubricants,
473 including variable protein concentrations, hyaluronic acid, and phospholipid mixtures, may provide a
474 more comprehensive understanding of hydrogel behavior in joint-mimicking environments. Future
475 work could therefore explore the tribological response under progressively more complex biochemical
476 conditions.

477

478 **5. Conclusion**

479 This study provided a comparative evaluation of PVA and pHEMA hydrogels with respect to their
480 structural, mechanical and biotribological performance in model conditions mimicking the articular
481 cartilage environment. The key findings can be summarized as follows:

- 482 - PVA hydrogels demonstrated ultra-low friction coefficients ($COF < 0.01$) and high swelling
483 ratios (~230%), attributed to their hydroxyl-rich polymer structure and strong surface
484 hydration.
- 485 - pHEMA hydrogels exhibited 3–10 times higher COF values but showed excellent wear
486 resistance under long-term sliding, likely due to higher stiffness and lower surface
487 permeability.
- 488 - Friction and wear behavior were closely linked to the chemical composition, hydration affinity,
489 and polymerization conditions of the hydrogels.
- 490 - The biotribological performance of PVA is favorable for load-bearing cartilage replacement but
491 may be limited by wear in longer-term applications.
- 492 - In contrast, pHEMA offers a structurally resilient platform, and its low wear potential under
493 load makes it an attractive candidate for further material tailoring, such as surface composition
494 and morphology modification or reinforcement.

495 These results underscore the importance of balancing friction/lubrication and structural integrity in
496 hydrogel design, and establish pHEMA as a mechanically resilient and chemically versatile platform for
497 the development of advanced cartilage-mimicking systems, with high potential for further
498 optimization through the incorporation of bioactive additives such as hyaluronic acid or phospholipids.

499

500 **Data Availability**

501 Supplementary data associated with this article can be found online as Dataset at Zenodo: DOI:

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503

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508

509 **Author's contributions**

510 DNec, DNem, JG, ZK, IC, MT wrote the original article; DNem, JG, DR, ZK, IC, MT, PaC, PeC, LS performed
511 experiments and conceived the data; LV, MV formulated hypotheses; DNec, LV, MV supervised
512 master's and PhD students; IK, MH supervised the study and provided funding. All the authors read
513 and approved the final version of the manuscript.

514

515 **Declaration of Conflict of Interests**

516 The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships
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518

519 **References**

- 520 [1] J.-R. Kim, Y.S. Cho, J.-H. Park, T.-H. Kim, Poly(HEMA-co-MMA) hydrogel scaffold for tissue
521 engineering with controllable morphology and mechanical properties through self-assembly,
522 *Polymers*. 16 (2024).
- 523 [2] F. Yang, J. Zhao, W.J. Koshut, J. Watt, J.C. Riboh, K. Gall, et al., A synthetic hydrogel composite with
524 the mechanical behavior and durability of cartilage, *Advanced Functional Materials*. 30 (2020).
- 525 [3] W. Lin, J. Klein, Recent progress in cartilage lubrication, *Advanced Materials*. 33 (2021).
- 526 [4] A. Suzuki, S. Sasaki, T. Murakami, Development of PVA hydrogels with superior lubricity for
527 artificial cartilage, *Rheology of Biological Soft Matter*. (2017) 339-374.
- 528 [5] R.E.D. Rudge, E. Scholten, J.A. Dijkstra, Natural and induced surface roughness determine
529 frictional regimes in hydrogel pairs, *Tribology International*. 141 (2020).
- 530 [6] J. Zhao, H. Tong, A. Kirillova, W.J. Koshut, A. Malek, N.C. Brigham, M.L. Becker, K. Gall, B.J. Wiley,
531 A Synthetic Hydrogel Composite with a Strength and Wear Resistance Greater than Cartilage,
532 *Advanced Functional Materials*. 32 (2022).
- 533 [7] S. Kim, Y. Hwang, M. Kashif, D. Jeong, G. Kim, Evaluation of bone regeneration on
534 polyhydroxyethyl-polymethyl methacrylate membrane in a rabbit calvarial defect model, *In Vivo*.
535 30 (2016) 587-591.
- 536 [8] Y. Wang, X. Chu, Y. Sun, P. Teng, T. Xia, Y. Chen, A convenient approach by using poly-(scPHEMA-
537 co-NIPAM/scp)/Cu²⁺ solution sol-gel transition for wound protection and healing, *Journal Of*
538 *Biomedical Materials Research Part B: Applied Biomaterials*. 109 (2020) 50-59.
- 539 [9] R. Ghanbarinia Firozjah, A. Sadeghi, S. Khoei, Ultrasonic de-cross-linking of the pH- and magneto-
540 responsive PHEMA/PMMA microgel to Janus nanoparticles: A new synthesis based on “grafting
541 from”/“grafting to” polymerization, *ACS Omega*. 5 (2020) 27119-27132.
- 542 [10] T. Krajňák, E. Černá, M. Šuráňová, T. Šamožil, D. Zicha, L. Vojtová, et al., Replica-mold
543 nanopatterned PHEMA hydrogel surfaces for ophthalmic applications, *Scientific Reports*. 12
544 (2022).

- 545 [11] C.S.A. Musgrave, F. Fang, Contact lens materials: A materials science perspective, *Materials*. 12
546 (2019) 261.
- 547 [12] M. Zare, A. Bigham, M. Zare, H. Luo, E. Rezvani Ghomi, S. Ramakrishna, PHEMA: An overview for
548 biomedical applications, *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*. 22 (2021) 6376.
- 549 [13] Z. Kadlecová, I. Chamradová, K. Tušlová, D. Rebenda, P. Čípek, J. Gregora, et al., Biomimetic
550 pHEMA hydrogels as an alternative cartilage-like model material for biotribological evaluations,
551 Zenodo Preprint. (2025). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16537707>
- 552 [14] Z. Hua, M. Hu, Y. Chen, X. Huang, L. Gao, Investigation of the friction properties of a new artificial
553 imitation cartilage material: PHEMA/glycerol gel, *Materials*. 16 (2023) 4023.
- 554 [15] S. Yarimitsu, S. Sasaki, T. Murakami, A. Suzuki, Evaluation of lubrication properties of hydrogel
555 artificial cartilage materials for joint prosthesis, *Biosurface and Biotribology*. 2 (2016) 40-47.
- 556 [16] Y. Xi, P.K. Sharma, H.J. Kaper, C.-H. Choi, Tribological properties of micropored poly(2-
557 hydroxyethyl methacrylate) hydrogels in a biomimetic aqueous environment, *ACS Applied*
558 *Materials & Interfaces*. 13 (2021) 41473-41484.
- 559 [17] T. Murakami, S. Yarimitsu, K. Nakashima, Y. Sawae, N. Sakai, Influence of synovia constituents on
560 tribological behaviors of articular cartilage, *Friction*. 1 (2013) 150-162.
- 561 [18] L. Bostan, A.-M. Trunfio-Sfarghiu, L. Verestiuc, M.I. Popa, F. Munteanu, J.-P. Rieu, et al.,
562 Mechanical and tribological properties of poly(hydroxyethyl methacrylate) hydrogels as articular
563 cartilage substitutes, *Tribology International*. 46 (2012) 215-224.
- 564 [19] D. Němeček, D. Nečas, H. Shinmori, S. Yarimitsu, M. Marian, M. Vrbka, et al., A glance into the
565 boundary lubrication mechanism of PVA hydrogel after the reduction of interstitial fluid
566 pressurization, *Friction*. (2025) doi: 10.26599/frict.2025.9441106.
- 567 [20] E. Karadag, D. Saraydin, N. Sahiner, O. Güven, Radiation induced acrylamide/citric acid hydrogels
568 and their swelling behaviors, *Journal of Macromolecular Science Part A*. 38 (2001) 1105-1121.
- 569 [21] E. Manaila, G. Craciun, D. Ighigeanu, C. Cimpeanu, C. Barna, V. Fugaru, Hydrogels synthesized by
570 electron beam irradiation for heavy metal adsorption, *Materials*. 10 (2017) 540.

- 571 [22] L.C. Duque-Ossa, G. Ruiz-Pulido, D.I. Medina, Triborheological study under physiological
572 conditions of PVA hydrogel/HA lubricant as synthetic system for soft tissue replacement,
573 *Polymers*. 13 (2021) 746.
- 574 [23] I.-A. Plugariu, M. Bercea, L.M. Gradinaru, D. Rusu, A. Lupu, Poly(vinyl alcohol)/pullulan composite
575 hydrogels as a potential platform for wound dressing applications, *Gels*. 9 (2023) 580.
- 576 [24] C.M. Hassan, N.A. Peppas, Cellular PVA hydrogels produced by freeze/thawing, *Journal of Applied*
577 *Polymer Science*. 76 (2000) 2075-2079.
- 578 [25] E. Otsuka E, A. Suzuki, Swelling properties of physically cross-linked PVA gels prepared by a cast-
579 drying method, *Gels: Structures, Properties, and Functions*. (2009) 121-126.
- 580 [26] A.S. Oliveira, R. Colaço, A.P. Serro, Hydrogels based on poly(vinyl alcohol) for cartilage
581 substitution, *Annals of Medicine*. 53 (2021) 2069-2089.
- 582 [27] A.K. Bajpai, R. Saini, Preparation and characterization of biocompatible spongy cryogels of
583 poly(vinyl alcohol)-gelatin and study of water sorption behaviour, *Polymer International*. 54
584 (2005) 1233-1242.
- 585 [28] R. Aversa, R.V. Petrescu, F.I.T. Petrescu, V. Perrotta, D. Apicella, A. Apicella, Biomechanically
586 tunable nano-silica/P-HEMA structural hydrogels for bone scaffolding, *Bioengineering*. 8 (2021)
587 45.
- 588 [29] G. Mabillean, M.F. Baslé, D. Chappard, Evaluation of surface roughness of hydrogels by fractal
589 texture analysis during swelling, *Langmuir*. 22 (2006) 4843-4845.
- 590 [30] Y. Zhong, Q. Lin, H. Yu, L. Shao, X. Cui, Q. Pang, et al., Construction methods and biomedical
591 applications of PVA-based hydrogels, *Frontiers in Chemistry*. 12 (2024) 1398712.
- 592 [31] P.N. Charron, T.A. Braddish, R. Floreani, PVA-gelatin hydrogels formed using combined theta-gel
593 and cryo-gel fabrication techniques, *Journal of the Mechanical Behavior of Biomedical Materials*.
594 92 (2019) 90-96.

- 595 [32] P. Zhang, Z. Xu, Z. Wu, P. Xu, C. Yang, Strengthening poly(2-hydroxyethyl methacrylate) hydrogels
596 using biochars and hydrophobic aggregations, *International Journal of Smart and Nano Materials*.
597 13 (2022) 561-574.
- 598 [33] T. Jayaramudu, H.-U. Ko, H.C. Kim, J.W. Kim, R.M. Muthoka, J. Kim, Electroactive hydrogels made
599 with polyvinyl alcohol/cellulose nanocrystals, *Materials*. 11 (2018) 1615.
- 600 [34] T. Murakami, N. Sakai, S. Yarimitsu, K. Nakashima, T. Yamaguchi, Y. Sawae, et al., Evaluation of
601 influence of changes in permeability with aging on friction and biphasic behaviors of artificial
602 hydrogel cartilage, *Biotribology*. 26 (2021) 100178.
- 603 [35] S. Yarimitsu, Y. Sawae, Development of PVA hydrogels for artificial cartilage with superior lubricity,
604 *Proceedings of JSME International Conference on Materials and Processing*. (2022) Okinawa,
605 Japan.
- 606 [36] N. Sakai, C. Hashimoto, S. Yarimitsu, Y. Sawae, M. Komori, T. Murakami, A functional effect of the
607 superficial mechanical properties of articular cartilage as a load bearing system in a sliding
608 condition, *Biosurface and Biotribology*. 2 (2016) 26-39.
- 609 [37] R. Simič, J. Mandal, K. Zhang, N.D. Spencer, Oxygen inhibition of free-radical polymerization is the
610 dominant mechanism behind the “mold effect” on hydrogels, *Soft Matter*. 17 (2021) 6394-6403.
- 611 [38] R. Simič, N.D. Spencer, Controlling the friction of gels by regulating interfacial oxygen during
612 polymerization, *Tribology Letters*. 69 (2021).
- 613 [39] D. Hu, Y. Yan, W. Wei, C. Bai, Y. Lu, Y. Wang, et al., Mechanically robust lubricating hydrogels
614 contrived by harnessing low-entropy nanocrystalline polymer network, *Advanced Functional*
615 *Materials*. 35 (2025) 2409023.
- 616 [40] N. Asy-Syifa, Kusjuriansah, W.X. Waresindo, D. Edikresnha, T. Suciati, K. Khairurrijal, The study of
617 the swelling degree of the PVA hydrogel with varying concentrations of PVA, *Journal of Physics:*
618 *Conference Series*. 2243 (2022) 012053.

- 619 [41] K. Ou, X. Dong, C. Qin, X. Ji, J. He, Properties and toughening mechanisms of PVA/PAM double-
620 network hydrogels prepared by freeze-thawing and anneal-swelling, *Materials Science and*
621 *Engineering: C*. 77 (2017) 1017-1026.
- 622 [42] J. Krzeminski, H. Molisak-Tolwinska, The structure of water-swollen poly(vinyl alcohol) and the
623 swelling mechanism, *Journal of Macromolecular Science: Part A - Chemistry*. 28 (1991) 413-429.
- 624 [43] M.A. Zitouni, B. Kara Slimane, Preparation and characterization of hydrogels based on
625 chitosan/polyvinyl alcohol blends, *Advanced Materials Research*. 1105 (2015) 203-207.
- 626 [44] T. Nakano, T. Nakaoki, Coagulation size of freezable water in poly(vinyl alcohol) hydrogels formed
627 by different freeze/thaw cycle periods, *Polymer Journal*. 43 (2011) 875-880.
- 628 [45] A. Chhatri, J. Bajpai, A.K. Bajpai, S.S. Sandhu, N. Jain, J. Biswas, Cryogenic fabrication of savlon
629 loaded macroporous blends of alginate and polyvinyl alcohol (PVA): swelling, deswelling and
630 antibacterial behaviors, *Carbohydrate Polymers*. 83 (2011) 876-882.
- 631 [46] O. Muratoglu, S. Spiegelberg, J. Ruberti, N. Abt, PVA hydrogel, U.S. Patent Application No. US
632 20060079597A1 (2006). United States Patent and Trademark Office.
- 633 [47] Y. Guan, J. Bian, F. Peng, X.-M. Zhang, R.-C. Sun, High strength of hemicelluloses-based hydrogels
634 by freeze/thaw technique, *Carbohydrate Polymers*. 101 (2014) 272-280.
- 635 [48] A. Chaturvedi, A.K. Bajpai, J. Bajpai, Preparation and characterization of poly(vinyl alcohol)
636 cryogel-silver nanocomposites and evaluation of blood compatibility, cytotoxicity, and
637 antimicrobial behaviors, *Polymer Composites*. 36 (2014) 1983-1997.
- 638 [49] A. Górska, E. Baran, J. Knapik-Kowalczyk, J. Szafraniec-Szczyński, M. Paluch, P. Kulinowski, et al.,
639 Physically cross-linked PVA hydrogels as potential wound dressings: How freezing conditions and
640 formulation composition define cryogel structure and performance, *Pharmaceutics*. 16 (2024)
641 1388.